

Situation Analysis and Risk Assessment for Network Security

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Abstract—With the expansion of computer networks, the proliferation of malicious network activities presents considerable risks to the operational integrity of many businesses and imposes heavy cost tolls on life and health. Therefore, risk assessment is highly essential in network security management and analysis. Network security situation analysis not only can explain the current state but also project the forthcoming behavior of the network. Alerts originating from IDS, Firewall, and other security solutions are now emerging at a rapid rate. Large corporations are having problems keeping on top of the current status of their networks. In this research, we described cyberspace situational awareness from formal and visual methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

Network security estimation is to detect computer system or network facilities to uncover security holes and vulnerability maybe imposed by hacker, take steps sooner, and defend network system from threats. [1] The current Researches on network security scenario have two big classes of depending on system deployment and operating information according to data resources . The former is about system design, deployment, service and hidden problems in the system. The latter is about attacking conditions on the system mostly through IDS logs database. Security scenario assessment work based on system operating information is largely about threat estimation from single incident on the system. Bass presented that next generation cyberspace intrusion detection systems will fuse data from heterogeneous distributed network sensors to create cyberspace situational awareness, and multisensor data fusion technology is an important avenue on the road toward the development of highly reliable intrusion detection and security-decision systems that identify, track, and assess cyberspace situations with multiple complex threats .[2] But result only gives tiny stages in the process of determining the technical criteria to build and create cyberspace situational awareness systems. Chen Xiuzhen created a quantitative hierarchical threat assessment model and computational approach based on the structure of the network and the relevance of services and hosts to evaluate security threat status of a computer network system . [3]. [4] Because assaults are dynamic, if analysts can't assimilate and correlate the available data, it is impossible for them to detect complex attacks. Developing tools that raise the situational awareness and comprehension of all those responsible for the network's safe operation may boost a computer network's overall security. System administrators are often confined to textual or rudimentary graphical representations of network activities. There is a growing corpus of research

that confirms the usefulness of visualization as a technique for tackling complicated data challenges. Yarden and Stefano focus on visual correlation of network alarms and situational awareness .[5] The National Center for Supercomputing Apps (NCSA) has created two applications for the identification of network incidents: VisFlowConnect [6] and NVisionIP .[7] They acquire Internet security scenario according to visualization of connection analysis and system status. Network is a system; security is a process not a product. So assessing network risk and estimating scenario should be from the system point of view, no more than analyze security state dependent on particular security instrument. For instance, virus scanners target dangerous material, vulnerability scanners offer information on chances to exploit systems, intrusion detection systems identify unusual activity, and misuse detectors highlight policy breaches. [8] System vulnerabilities are gaps in the software or hardware of a server or a client that may be exploited by a determined intruder to obtain access to or shut down a network. Donald Pipkin defines system vulnerability as a state, a weakness of or a lack of security mechanism, or technological, physical, or other controls that might be exploited by a threat Vulnerabilities occur not only in the hardware and software that compose a computer system but also in rules and processes, notably security policies and procedures, that are utilized in a computer network system and in users and employees of the computer network systems. Since vulnerabilities may be discovered in so many places in a network system, one might conclude that a security vulnerability is actually anything in a computer network that has the potential to cause or be exploited for an advantage. [9]

II. AWARENESS OF CYBERSPACE SITUATIONS

Oswald Boelke first acknowledged the idea of situation awareness during World War I. He understood "the need of being aware of the adversary before the enemy became similarly aware, and established techniques for doing so." The fundamental principle behind situational awareness is the discrepancy between what a human operator believes the system state to be and what the system really is. [10]

Situational awareness, which is about having a better understanding of your surroundings, comes from conventional combat. It is emphasized through an emphasis on significant environmental components that situational awareness is always about doing something. Cyber Situational Awareness is a

Fig. 1: AWARENESS OF CYBERSPACE SITUATIONS

notion that applies when there is a cyber environment (CSA). [11]

Situational awareness (SA) enables decision-makers within an organization to have the knowledge and understanding needed to make wise choices while carrying out their duties. It may be more general in scope or more narrowly focused on assisting individuals and organizations in safeguarding their digital assets. In order to assist people make better choices, SA enables the collection of pertinent information from throughout an organization, its integration, and dissemination .[12]

III. CLEAR EXPLANATION

Endsley described situational awareness as "the observation of the elements in the environment with a volume of time and space, understanding their significance, and projecting their state in the near future." the official

The three layers of the security situational assessment definition are broken down. Refinement of security situation elements at level 1: The virus scanner, misuse detector, IDS, and Firewall are sources of refined data. As an n-tuple,[13] we formalize it.

$$S = [T_1, T_2, T_3, T_4, T_5, T_6, \dots, T_n]$$

where S is a period-specific information vector.

T represents feature data from a variety of security technologies, including alarms, logs, and audit data. Situation space is a component of the information vectors gathered through ongoing security technologies. A few warning kinds are refined from a large number of security events in the process of refining feature vector V, which is how security scenario features are refined. Level 2 understanding of the current circumstance: Explain and estimate the network's current security state using the alert track A and the V created from level 1. Based on a continuous reached feature vector, A is updated.

the whole network environment

$$\theta = [A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, \dots]$$

An element of them is the potential appearance of alarm tracks.

The set of feature vectors for the currently attained condition is:

Fig. 2: Awareness of Security situations

$M = [V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_5, V_6, \dots, V_n]$. The process of understanding the current circumstance entails finding a mapping.

$$F : M \rightarrow \theta$$

Level 3 forecast of the network security environment:

$$\theta$$

From level 2, predict the network security scenario in the future and show the trend of network security using probability. That is a security-seeking scenario.

$$\theta(t + \Delta t)$$

of

$$(t + \Delta t)$$

clock in accordance with the scenario of

$$\theta(t)$$

of t. Finding a mapping is necessary to project the future state of network security:

$$\varphi \theta(t) \rightarrow \theta(t + \Delta t)$$

Figure 2 shows the connection between various layers of security situational assessment, the mental model, and making-choices.

Fig. 3: Domain for Security Alerts

Fig. 4: mapping in visual form

IV. VERIFICATION

The majority of modern information security technologies concentrate on discrete issues rather than the overall picture. The assessment of the security situation can be advanced by visualization. Visualization, for instance, allows for the simultaneous examination of multiple occurrences.

Textual or tabular format, on the other hand, focuses on specifics and deep examination of a small number of events or characteristics, which is useful for analyzing events sequentially but difficult to observe all the security occurrences at once. The initial presentation of system logs or IDS logs uses visualization. But real-time transformation is not possible. Therefore, a visualization system with data flow, many sources, and several views is offered for assessing the network security state. [14]

V. SIMILARITY

Correlating the vast number of security events from multiple security instruments is important in the process of fine-tuning scenario characteristics at level 1. Using visual correlation, Yarden showed. The foundation of their strategy was to display network alerts as links between two domains. As illustrated in Figure 3, one represents node property and the other is a two-dimensional domain expressing time and type attribute. As illustrated in Figure 4, map the node domain into a finite circle, then encircle it with a ring of type-time domain. [15]

The apparent absence of common grounds on which to establish any sort of comparison across warnings is the fundamental obstacle to correlating alerts from different logs. Alerts must have what they refer to as the W^3 in Yarden's technique.

Time, node, and type are the what, where, and when properties. In level 2 of the security situation assessment, a few alert kinds were refined from a significant number of security events in level 1, creating alert tracks A. Using in our design

Figure 5 shows how the parallel axes view depicts correlations between security events from various security instru-

Fig. 5: Parallel axes are represented by correlations.

ments. When a new assault event occurs, it will assess existing alert tracks and determine whether to join those that are similar or to create a new one. The number on the alert track axis will change to $n+1$ whenever a new one is created. If it has ancient joints made a line between the event and the alert track, first. A darker or thicker line denotes a higher correlation between occurrences and an alert track. The security administrator's attention will be drawn to this, enabling them to act and fix the issue on the suspicious system.

VI. THE PARTS SITUATION ANALYSIS PLAYS IN NETWORK SECURITY RISK ANALYSIS

Security evaluation is a system project, as was previously stated. The purpose of a security risk assessment is to identify present and potential risks, gauge security threats and the amount to which they have an impact, and give general guidance for the creation of security policies and the setup and operation of information systems. [16] Situation analysis predicts future events from three levels, not just a single security incident or alert, by estimating the network's current status. Consequently, situation analysis aids in the advancement of network security evaluation. [17]

VII. CONCLUSION

Security policy is established and adjusted based on the security risk assessment, which is a crucial management tool used throughout the whole information system process. In this essay, we spoke about risk estimate and scenario evaluation. Three steps of refinement, understanding, and projection are outlined for scenario assessment in order to comprehend the network situation, identify vulnerabilities, and project the future situation. With the use of this situational analysis, we can identify unusual network activity and close security gaps to thwart attackers before they have a chance to do significant harm. As a result, network situation analysis and risk assessment study both heavily rely on visualization and its association.

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